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SHAMS AL-DIN ELDENIZ'S POLITICAL ACTIVITIES AND NAKHCHIVAN

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Abstract

The article discusses the political activities of Shams al-Din Eldiguz, the founder of the Atabey dynasty of Azerbaijan. It notes that during his time, he operated within the Seljuk Empire, which had already lost its power, and the Iraq Seljuk Sultanate, which was dependent on it. Sultan Mas'ud of the Iraq Seljuks valued him highly, entrusting him with the rule of Arran and the tutelage of Malik Arslan Shah. After being appointed as the Atabey of Arran, Shams al-Din Eldiguz tirelessly fought as a commander and ruler to thwart political processes and the Georgian invasions into Azerbaijan. He also influenced the political activities of the Iraq Seljuk sultans, establishing relations with the rulers of Rey and Maragheh as well as the Atabegs of Fars.

Keywords: Shams al-Din Eldeniz, Azerbaijan, city of Nakhchivan, Arslan Shah, Atabegs of Arran

Introduction. After the decline of the Great Seljuk state, several sultanates emerged that were subordinate to it. One of these was the Iraq Seljuk Sultanate (1194-1194). Azerbaijan was also one of the territories under the control of the Iraq Seljuk Sultanate. A special Atabey regime existed within the Seljuk state, focusing on the education of princes. These Atabegs paid particular attention to the training and upbringing of royal offspring. One such Atabey was Shams al-Din Eldiguz, the founder of the Atabey dynasty of Azerbaijan. His role as a state leader is evidenced by his relationships with neighboring rulers, his struggle against the Georgians who invaded Azerbaijan, and his administration of the Iraq Seljuk Sultanate in the name of Arslan Shah, which illustrates the challenges and responsibilities of his rule. Moreover, Shams al-Din Eldiguz lived in Nakhchivan, conducting his governance from there, which contributed to the city becoming one of the main socio-economic and cultural centers of the period.

The Early Years of Shams al-Din Eldiguz. Detailed information about Shams al-Din Eldiguz mainly comes from his appointment as the ruler of Arran. Prior to this, there is very little information available about him. It is known that he was purchased in the slave market of Derbent by Abu Hamid Ali ibn Ahmad al-Sumayrimi, the vizier of the Iraq Seljuk Sultan Mahmud (1118-1131). Shams al-Din Eldiguz caught the vizier's attention with his intelligence and astuteness, leading the vizier to take an interest in his upbringing. In May 1122, after the assassination of al-Sumayrimi by the Ismailis, Shams al-Din Eldiguz became part of the sultan's property along with all of the vizier's possessions. This marked his entry into the service of the sultan. Shams al-Din Eldiguz distinguished himself in the sultan's court through his intelligence and acumen, eventually rising to the position of emir-i chashnigir (the person in charge of the food service). Based on this information, we can conclude that Shams al-Din Eldiguz was one of the important and influential figures in the sultan's court.

Sources refer to Shams al-Din Eldiguz by the epithets "al-Sanjari" and "al-Masudi." For instance, the historian Juzjani (1193-1262) noted that Shams al-Din

Eldiguz was among the subjects of Sultan Sanjar [3, p. 355; 29, p. 170].

Sources attribute the rise in Shams al-Din Eldiguz's influence at the sultan's court to his non-involvement in any internal factions within the palace. It is even noted that he consistently sat in the same place during the divan sessions [1, p. 49; 12, p. 13]. All these orderly behaviors did not go unnoticed by the sultan.

The Historical Context of Shams al-Din Eldiguz. Looking at the history of the Iraq Seljuk Sultanate, we see that during the reign of Sultan Mas'ud (1135-1152), the ruler of Arran was Atabey Qara Sunqur (1131-1141). He was the most influential emir of the Iraq Seljuk Sultanate and the first to receive the title of great atabey in the history of the Arran Atabeyate. Sultan Mas'ud, wary of Qara Sunqur's power, attempted to overthrow him, but this plot failed, and Qara Sunqur's influence and strength only grew. In 1136, during the Ganja earthquake, Atabey Qara Sunqur traveled from Nakhchivan, where he resided, to Ganja to save the population from Georgian plunder and slaughter. He did not leave Ganja after the earthquake and continued to live there, but he died in 1141 due to a disease that spread in the city. After Qara Sunqur, Amir Chavli (1141-1146) was appointed as the ruler of Arran. However, his rule was short-lived, as he died suddenly, which changed the situation. The sultan then appointed Fakhr al-Din Togan Yureki (1146-1147), who had been the iqta holder of Khalkhal and Azerbaijan, in his place, aiming to deter opposition by appointing Togan Yureki to Arran. When Fakhr al-Din Togan Yureki arrived in Arran, he requested that both Khass-bey and Shams al-Din Eldiguz accompany him. Sultan Mas'ud formed an alliance with Shams al-Din Eldiguz and Khass-bey. Due to this alliance, Togan Yureki was killed on the orders of Amir Khass-bey during his struggle against the Georgians. Historians such as Ravandi (?-1207) and Mirkhond (1433-1498) indicate that Shams al-Din Eldiguz also participated in this event, while al-Husayni (12th century) and al-Isfahani (?-1201) mention only Amir Khass-bey. After Togan Yureki, Sultan Mas'ud appointed Amir Khass-bey as the ruler of Arran, but his rule was also brief. There are various accounts in the scholarly literature regarding the date of Shams al-Din

Eldiguz's appointment as the ruler of Arran. Academic Ziya Bunyadov states this event took place in 1136 [1, p. 49], while some other studies suggest the date as 1146 [5, p. 197; 12, p. 13; 28, p. 1110]. Historian Mirkhond mentions that Shams al-Din Eldiguz was appointed as the ruler of Arran and Azerbaijan after Qara Sunqur's death [21, p. 210], while Ibn al-Athir references him as the ruler of Arran, Ganja, and Qaysar (Qisār, a village near Marand) during the events of 543 AH [2, p. 151; 9, p. 36; 3, p. 355]. After being appointed ruler of Arran, Shams al-Din Eldiguz is said to have lived in Bard with his family [10, p. 75]. As one of the trusted emirs of the sultan, he married Mo'mina Khātūn, the wife of II Toghrul. From this marriage, Shams al-Din Eldiguz had two sons (Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan and Qızıl Arslan) and a daughter [23, p. 160]. While sources mention the existence of Shams al-Din Eldiguz's daughter, there are no further details about her. In a short time, Shams al-Din Eldiguz established his authority in Arran. His constant adversary was the Georgians, who seized every opportunity to raid the cities of Azerbaijan.

Death Following the death of Sultan Mas'ud (AH 550/1150-1151), a power struggle erupted within the Iraq Seljuk Sultanate. Sultan Mas'ud's nephew, Malik Shah (1152-1153), ascended to power but was quickly overthrown. A power contest emerged between Suleiman Shah (1153, 1159-1161) and Sultan Muhammad (1153-1159). Among the Seljuk emirs, Amir Aqsungur al-Hamadani was brought to Azerbaijan to protect Arslan Shah (1161-1177) [9, p. 214; 13, p. 94; 24, p. 160]. Notably, Arslan Shah's mother, Mo'mina Khātūn, was the wife of Shams al-Din Eldiguz. Shams al-Din Eldiguz supported Suleiman Shah, who was ultimately defeated. Sultan Muhammad indicated that he would pardon Shams al-Din Eldiguz in exchange for his son, Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan, as a hostage. However, influenced by Caliph al-Muqtafi (1136-1160), Shams al-Din Eldiguz refused to submit, as Arslan Shah's rise to power would have strengthened his own position. In 1157, battles occurred near Ray and in Nakhchivan between Sultan Muhammad and Shams al-Din Eldiguz, both of which ended in victories for Sultan Muhammad. Despite Shams al-Din Eldiguz's opposition, Sultan Muhammad forgave him and appointed him as the ruler of Arran [15, p. 368; 1, p. 44-45; 6, p. 23-24]. In AH 552 (1157-1158), when Sultan Muhammad launched an invasion into Iraq, all the emirs participated except for Shams al-Din Eldiguz. Historian al-Husayni notes that he could not join the campaign due to Georgian attacks on Azerbaijan [13, p. 94]. In 1152, Sultan Muhammad executed his vizier Khass-bey and sent the head to Shams al-Din Eldiguz and the ruler of Maragha, Nasreddin Aqsungur. The sultan aimed to eliminate the emirs' tendencies to distance themselves from central authority. Instead of fearing this, the emirs distanced themselves from Sultan Muhammad and gravitated toward Suleiman Shah [11, p. 209]. Shams al-Din Eldiguz was in Hamadan with other emirs during Suleiman Shah's struggle for power. However, Suleiman Shah's debauchery alienated the emirs, and Shams al-Din Eldiguz was among the first to break away, as conflicts among the emirs began while he was

not in Azerbaijan. The most dangerous of these emirs was Amir Ravvad (the nephew of Amir Khass-bey), who seized control of Azerbaijan by exploiting Shams al-Din Eldiguz's absence. Upon returning to Azerbaijan, Shams al-Din Eldiguz's first act was to expel Ravvad from the region [11, p. 209; 1, p. 43-44]. After Sultan Muhammad, Sultan Suleiman came to power, with his vizier Shihab al-Din Sika and hacib Muzaffar al-Din Alparq. Historian Fazlullah Rashid al-Din notes that to win Shams al-Din Eldiguz's favor, Sultan Suleiman declared Malik Arslan as the heir apparent [25, p. 242].

Shams al-Din Eldiguz's Relations with the Georgians. In 1161, the political situation in the Iraq Seljuk Sultanate was tense, primarily due to the accession of Arslan Shah, which caused discontent among several emirs. During this turmoil, Shams al-Din Eldiguz was in Hamadan alongside Arslan Shah. Seizing this opportunity, the Georgian forces led by King George III (1156-1184) launched an attack on Ani in 1161. Seyf al-Din Bey-Teymuri, the ruler of Khilat, attempted to assist Ani but was defeated due to the overwhelming strength of the Georgian troops, who captured many prisoners [2, p. 151-152; 22, p. 72]. After sacking Ani, the Georgians turned their attention to Dvin (or Debil). Shams al-Din Eldiguz, upon hearing of the Georgian advances toward Ganja, mobilized his forces for a counterattack. He formed an alliance with other Muslim emirs, including Seyf al-Din Bey-Teymuri of Khilat, Nusr al-Din Arslan-Aba of Maragha, and Fakhr al-Din of Erzincan, and launched a campaign against the Georgians in 1163 [2, p. 152]. Initially, the Georgians were defeated near Dvin, leading to the liberation of the city. Overall, Shams al-Din Eldiguz concluded this campaign successfully, returning with victories and spoils. Following the campaign, a Georgian prince, Elikum, was sent to the court of Shams al-Din Eldiguz as part of a peace agreement. An anonymous Georgian author noted that Shams al-Din Eldiguz played a key role as a mediator between the sultan (Arslan Shah) and the Georgian king in these negotiations [14, p. 352]. Shams al-Din Eldiguz entrusted the administration of the city of Miyana to Elikum. During the time of Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan, the governance of Nakhchivan, Julfa, and Alinjaghala was also handed over to him, with Elikum converting to Islam [1, p. 61; 31, p. 922]. Historian al-Husayni offers slightly different accounts regarding the Georgian attacks on Ani, Dvin, and Ganja. He states that Shams al-Din Eldiguz received news of the Georgian assaults while in Hamadan. As he prepared to return to Azerbaijan, he received a letter from the Georgian noble demanding tribute from Ganja and Beylagan. Hearing this, Sultan Arslan Shah summoned all his emirs to Nakhchivan and launched a campaign against Georgia. The battle near the Lukri fortress (also referred to as Kak fortress by Hamdullah Qazvini) resulted in a Georgian defeat [13, p. 111-114; 15, p. 369; 26, p. 81; 23, p. 53]. This indicates that Nakhchivan was not only a center for the Atabegs but also played a crucial role as a key point for the Iraq Seljuk sultans in Azerbaijan.

From the year 1166, a brief period of calm began in the relations between the Georgians and the Eldiguz-

ids. The next Georgian campaigns took place in the Islamic year 569 [1173-1174]. According to the historian Ravandi, Mo'mina Khātūn traveled from Azerbaijan to Hamadan to inform the sultan about the Abkhazian raids. However, academic Ziya Bunyadov further clarifies this information, stating that Mo'mina Khātūn minə Khatun traveled from Nakhchivan to Hamadan [24, p. 284; 1, p. 64]. Historian Rauf Mammadov notes that Mo'mina Khātūn went to Hamadan from Nakhchivan to persuade Arslan Shah [4, p. 74]. Later, Sultan Arslan Shah gathered troops and came from Hamadan to Nakhchivan, where he celebrated Eid al-Adha. Arslan Shah, preparing to attack Georgia (Ravandi and Al-Husayni referred to the Georgians as "Abkhazians"), fell ill and went to the Kiliya fortress with his mother (Mo'mina Khātūn). Shortly after, they moved from Kiliya to Dvin and then to the banks of the Aras River. It became known that the plague had spread among the army, and the disease caused significant losses. Despite this disaster, the sultan's army achieved victory. The allies captured the Aghsheher Fortress (located near Lake Childir, along the Kars-Akhalsikhe road, known as Tetriz-Tsikhe Fortress). After this victory, Arslan Shah returned to Nakhchivan and stayed there for about 50 days [24, p. 284-285; 32, p. 149-150; 1, p. 64].

In October 1174, the Georgians once again attacked the city of Ani and captured it. Although Shams al-Din Eldeniz sent troops towards Ani at that time, they were defeated. Shortly after, Eldeniz launched a campaign against the Georgians, and the two sides confronted each other near Dvin. However, no military engagement took place [1, p. 65]. Unwilling to accept this failure, Eldeniz, in the following year, led an expedition to Georgia, accompanied by Sultan Arslan Shah, the ruler of Khilat Seyfeddin Bey-Teymuri, and the armies of Diyarbakir led by his sons Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan (1175-1186) and Qizil Arslan (1186-1191). Eldeniz successfully returned to Nakhchivan after this campaign [1, p. 65; 27, p. 544].

Shams al-Din Eldeniz's relations with the Atabegs of Fars, the ruler of Ray, and the Aqsunqurids of Maragha. Shams al-Din Eldeniz's relationship with Amir Inanj, the ruler of Ray, had been strained since the time of the struggle between Suleiman Shah and Sultan Muhammad. During that conflict, Shams al-Din Eldeniz and Amir Inanj were on opposing sides. As mentioned earlier, in this struggle (the battles of Ray and Nakhchivan), Suleiman Shah, whom Shams al-Din Eldeniz supported, was defeated [13, p. 99; 1, p. 45].

After Sultan Süleyman, Sultan Arslan Shah was brought to power, but the caliph and some emirs were not in agreement with this decision. The delegation sent by Shams al-Din Eldeniz to Baghdad was not recognized by Caliph Al-Mustanjid (1160-1170). Thus, a power struggle began between the sultanates. The caliph incited Amir Inanj, the ruler of Ray, Nusrat al-Din Aqsunqur, the ruler of Maragha (1133-1174), Sungur, the Atabeg of Fars (1148-1161), and other rulers into conflict. The emirs supported Prince Mahmud Shah and Malik Shah ibn Mahmud against Arslan Shah. Learning of these activities, Shams al-Din Eldeniz began to counter them. In 1161, Sultan Arslan Shah defeated the

emirs supporting Mahmud Shah. Amir Inanj took refuge in the Tabarak Fortress (in Ray). After this victory, Shams al-Din Eldeniz captured the city of Ray and granted it as an iqta to his son Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan. Amir Inanj, the ruler of Ray, accepted vassal dependence on Sultan Arslan Shah and strengthened relations by marrying his daughter to Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan [11, p. 262; 1, p. 41; 19, p. 324]. Despite his familial ties with Shams al-Din Eldeniz, Amir Inanj supported the activities of Atabeg Zangi in 1161. To put an end to these actions, Sultan Arslan Shah and Shams al-Din Eldeniz first attacked Ray. Amir Inanj's primary goal in this battle was to force Sultan Arslan Shah to fight without Shams al-Din Eldeniz [11, p. 263]. However, Shams al-Din Eldeniz arrived to assist Arslan Shah and turned the tide of the battle in their favor. In the battle between the combined forces of Sultan Arslan Shah and Shams al-Din Eldeniz, Amir Inanj hid in the Ray fortress and managed to escape. Historian Isfahani noted that Amir Inanj was residing in a mountain area on the Damghan border. The Georgians, taking advantage of Shams al-Din Eldeniz's presence in Ray, resumed their raids. As a result, he was unable to lay siege to Ray for an extended period. Shams al-Din Eldeniz and Sultan Arslan Shah accepted Amir Inanj's offer of peace. According to the terms of peace, Amir Inanj was required to pay tribute, and the territories of Cerbazekan and Saveh (located between Tehran and Hamadan) were taken from him and placed under the sultan's control. After neutralizing the threat of Amir Inanj, the sultan returned to Hamadan, while Shams al-Din Eldeniz returned to Nakhchivan [21, p. 242; 16, p. 223; 11, p. 263-264; 17, p. 53]. It is also worth noting that historian Isfahani mentioned that all power was in the hands of Shams al-Din Eldeniz, with the sultan serving only as a figurehead [11, p. 264-265]. Amir Inanj, in agreement with Khwarezmshah II-Arslan (1156-1172), intended to place Ray under the control of the Khwarezmshahs. Relying on II-Arslan, Amir Inanj ceased paying the required tribute. Upon learning of this alliance, Shams al-Din Eldeniz attacked Ray in 564 AH (1168/1169). Amir Inanj, seeking to renew his alliance with Shams al-Din Eldeniz, sent his vizier, Sadedin Ashallan, to negotiate. However, this time Sultan Arslan Shah and Shams al-Din Eldeniz refused to form an alliance and presented a condition to the vizier. According to Shams al-Din Eldeniz's terms, the vizier had to either go into exile with Amir Inanj or kill him and take control of Azerbaijan, Isfahan, and Ray under the rule of Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan. Vizier Sadedin Ashallan, using cunning, killed Amir Inanj, and Shams al-Din Eldeniz honored the promise he had made. Sources mention that during his service under Shams al-Din Eldeniz, Sadedin Ashallan was known as a just ruler [11, p. 269; 13, p. 105-108; 1, p. 69].

The Atabegate of Fars (1147-1284). After Arslan Shah came to power, Atabeg Eldeniz sent orders to the vassal atabegs and rulers, calling for their submission. However, wary of the growing strength of the Iraqi Seljuk Sultanate, the caliph encouraged some emirs to resist. The emirs who refused to submit requested the help of Muhammad ibn Tughrul through Sunqur ibn Madud. At the time, Muhammad ibn Tughrul was in

Shiraz, under the protection of Atabeg Sunqur. Atabeg Sunqur, following the demands of the opposition forces (led by Amir Inanj and his allies), joined their side [20, p. 322; 13, p. 102]. After Sultan Arslan Shah and Shams al-Din Eldeniz defeated the opposition forces, they prepared to attack Sunqur. However, Sunqur's death and his succession by his brother Zangi (1161-1175) changed the situation, as Zangi submitted to the sultan. This submission did not last long. Atabeg Zangi expelled Mahmud ibn Malik Shah from Istakhr Fortress (located in Shiraz), had the Friday prayers (khutbah) read in his own name, and became Mahmud's atabeg. At the same time, Atabeg Zangi joined forces with other emirs who were dissatisfied with the rule of Shams al-Din Eldeniz and the ruler of Ray, launching a rebellion. After Amir Inanj's defeat in 1161 and his submission to Shams al-Din Eldeniz, Atabeg Zangi found himself isolated on the battlefield. Realizing his precarious position, Zangi sent gifts of "swords, horses, robes, and jewels" to Shams al-Din Eldeniz and Sultan Arslan Shah, signaling his submission [6, p. 591; 24, p. 276-277]. To seek forgiveness, Atabeg Zangi personally traveled to meet Sultan Arslan Shah and Shams al-Din Eldeniz in Isfahan. He was first received by Shams al-Din Eldeniz and then presented to the sultan [24, p. 276-277; 18, p. 85].

Aqsunqurids (1117-1227). The relations between Shams al-Din Eldeniz and the representatives of the Aqsunqurids were not good from the very beginning. They often took opposing sides in the struggle for the throne among the Seljuk emirs. After Sultan Muhammad killed Amir Khasse-bey, Eldeniz and Nusrat al-Din Arslanaba were among the emirs who rose against him. They supported Suleiman Shah. Although it was for a short period, they were part of the same alliance. However, the dominion of Suleiman Shah distanced all the emirs from him. Sultan Muhammad pardoned Shams al-Din Eldeniz and Nusrat al-Din Arslanaba. In the year 549 AH, Shams al-Din Eldeniz and Nusrat al-Din Arslanaba divided Azerbaijan between themselves. This short-lived alliance lasted until Arslan Shah came to power. Among the opposing forces against Arslan Shah were the Aqsunqurids of Maragheh. Shams al-Din Eldeniz faced difficulties from Nusrat al-Din Arslanaba in his struggle against Amir Inanc. Nusrat al-Din Arslanaba provided troops to Amir Inanc in the conflict. After resolving relations with Amir Inanc, Shams al-Din Eldeniz directed his attention to the other non-submissive force, the Aqsunqurids. He invited the governor of Maragheh, Aqsunqur, to submit, but his refusal escalated the situation further. As a result, Shams al-Din Eldeniz sent troops to Maragheh under the leadership of Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan. Aqsunqur sought help from the governor of Xilat, Shah Armend. A battle occurred in 1161 near the Safid Rud River between the united forces of the allies and Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan. The battle ended in victory for the allies. Relations with the Maragheh governorship remained tense for a long time. Only during the reign of Shams al-Din Eldeniz's successors did the governorship of Maragheh submit.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the political activity of Shams al-Din Eldeniz, a prominent figure in Azerbaijan

during the 13th century, unfolded during a highly complex period. At this time, he operated within the diminishing Seljuk Empire and its vassal, the Iraqi Seljuk Sultanate. Notably, Sultan Mas'ud of the Iraqi Seljuks recognized Eldeniz's value, entrusting him with the governance of Arran and the regency of Malik Arslan Shah. Shams al-Din Eldeniz skillfully managed relations with neighboring rulers, establishing alliances through familial ties or military means to bring them under the control of the Iraqi Seljuk Sultanate. His rise to power caused significant concern among the Georgians, as they had previously conducted raids into Azerbaijan. However, under Eldeniz's leadership, these incursions were successfully repelled, and counter-offensive operations were organized against them. Overall, Shams al-Din Eldeniz's political maneuvers and military strategies played a crucial role in stabilizing and consolidating power in the region during a tumultuous time in history.

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